

Laboratory Safety Practices and Engagement of Junior High School Students in T.L.E. Classes

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Abstract. The researcher investigated whether the study aimed to determine the significant relationship between laboratory safety practices and engagement of learners in T.L.E. classes among the schools in the Division of Davao Oriental. The research utilized a quantitative research design, testing objective theories by examining the relationship among variables. The researcher employed a descriptive correlation research method using an adapted questionnaire as the research instrument for gathering the data. The statistical tools used in interpreting and analyzing the data were Mean, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson r , and Linear Regression. 130 junior high school students in the public secondary schools in the Division of Davao Oriental. The study's findings indicated that the extent of laboratory practices was high, and the extent of engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes was high. There was a significant relationship between laboratory safety practices and the engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes. These results revealed positive correlations between laboratory safety practices and the engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes. It was highly recommended that teachers incorporate Active learning strategies and achievement goals as domains of laboratory practices that significantly influence the engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes.

KEY WORDS

1. Laboratory Practices 2. Engagement 3. Technology Livelihood Education

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1. Introduction

For students to achieve maximum potential in learning, they need to be fully engaged in all learning undertakings under the facilitation of a teacher. Learning engagement determines how well a student performs academically and uplifts his social skills, which are crucial in his cognitive development; hence, one's learning engagement must be deemed indispensable by educators and given the utmost premium in instructional planning. Learning activities in this regard must be plotted so that students' engagement throughout the phases of instruction is sustained. In this regard, for TLE engagement, it is important to consider the safety of the learners. Lab safety equipment is essential to protect laboratory workers and ensure timely and accurate data collection. Understanding lab safety equipment and rules can prevent injury and create a successful and productive working environment. Safety practices observed by teachers in the context of classroom instruction and those regularly practiced by an academic community

in an institution to promote healthy and safe learning spaces are crucial in ensuring learners' engagement. As a general knowledge, safety is a necessity that must not be deemed optional but mandatory as this averts or thwarts an untoward incident that may put to perils the learners or the teaching personnel. Laboratories, where hands-on learning transpires, may pose multiple hazards that may discourage learners from engaging in the learning opportunities provided to them. Hence, Caymaz (2021), along this line, cited that this concern is realistic; effective learning requires laboratory experiments, but they must be appropriately organized because of the potential risks involved. When safety procedures are not taken, laboratory mishaps are unavoidable. These incidents could cause minor injuries or potentially significant outcomes, including fatalities. Ensuring laboratory safety is currently the prerequisite. In Beijing, China, the conditions of university laboratories could not match the demand for research as the number of graduate students increases, which could lead to dangerous behavior and potential risks. Furthermore, many laboratories have a high staff-to-capacity ratio, which increases the risk of major consequences and a higher death toll in the event of an accident. For instance, in a Beijing Jiaotong University laboratory in 2018, a significant explosion of magnesium powder resulted in the deaths of three students (Yang et al., 2019). Additionally, a university laboratory caught the attention of the entire country after learning of a severe laboratory explosion accident that took place therein and caused the death of a professor (Lixin, 2019). While this incident reminds us of the imminent danger in laboratories, people could not help but wonder why the incident happened despite the presence of an adult, an experienced teacher, who was handling the class. This shows that the risk in laboratories or similar learning spaces is almost inevitable. However, the perils may be reduced, and teachers and learners may be prepared for unfavorable circumstances. In the Philippines, the Department of Education continues to adopt mechanisms to ensure the provision of safe and protective learning spaces and school environments to provide a sound learning atmosphere that promotes the learning and well-being of both learners and teachers (Manila Bulletin, 2022). Such provision is in response to the current state of schools with unsafe learning environments across the country, which has remained unsolved due to inadequate, if not lack, funding. Public schools in the entire archipelago are still addressing problems relative to the safety and protection of the academic community. In the Davao Region, 2,698 private and public schools were ready as the school reverted to in-person classes after the restrictions in line with the COVID-19 outbreak were lifted (Sunstar Davao, 2022). Distance modular learning was adopted to protect learners from the threat of disease contagion. As the learners' presence in school endangers them from these threats, school officials are continuously finding solutions to these problems to ensure the overall welfare of learners as this helps promote desirable learning performance. As engagement of learners in the learning activities would mean providing them with a safe learning space, it was of prime concern by school authorities to forge partnerships with the community and other stakeholders and use available funds from the Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) budget allocations to defray the expense in building safe and protective structures for learners and other necessities that would guarantee their safety. In the Division of Davao Oriental, classrooms and schools, on the whole, pose risks to the school community and endanger the lives of learners despite the community's efforts to pre-empt untoward accidents. In response, schools, through their partnerships with stakeholders, have devised solutions to the safety and protection problems that may hamper students' learning. This, nonetheless, does

not mean that the problem has already been addressed, as partnerships may not always help respond to the assessed needs in schools. Schools in this division, therefore, are confronted with a challenge brought about by budget limitations. With the foregoing settings of the problem, the researcher sees the need to conduct the study to obtain the data needed to shed light on the currently existing problems and thereby help

school communities address them regarding the obtained data.

1.1. Statement of the Problem—This study aims to determine the significant relationship between laboratory safety practices and the engagement of learners in T.L.E. classes among the schools in the Division of Davao Oriental. Specifically, this sought answers to the following questions:

- (1) What is the level of laboratory safety practices of T.L.E classes in the high schools of Davao Oriental in terms of the following:
 - (1) Safety behavior;
 - (2) Safety Commitment; and
 - (3) Safety motivation?
- (2) What is the level of engagement of the junior high school students in T.L.E classes in the schools of Davao Oriental in terms of the following:
 - (1) Behavioral engagement;
 - (2) Cognitive Engagement; and
 - (3) Emotional Engagement?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between laboratory safety practices and the engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes?
- (4) Which of the domains of laboratory safety practices significantly influence the engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E classes?

1.2. Review of Significant Literature—This section presents key studies on laboratory safety practices and student engagement.

1.2.1. Laboratory Safety Practices—Laboratory safety is crucial in education, requiring skills and accountability to prevent accidents (Ida et al., 2020). Common issues include non-compliance with safety regulations and a lack of risk assessments (Su Hsu, 2019; Ayi Hon, 2018). Studies highlight the need for safety behavior, knowledge, and motivation in promoting safe laboratory environments (Neal et al., 2019; Goswami et al., 2011). Safety motivation encourages compliance with safety procedures, while safety commitment reduces accident rates (Griffin Neal, 2020; Salazar-Escoboza et al., 2020).

1.2.2. Student Engagement—Engagement in learning is vital for academic success, encom-

passing behavioral, cognitive, and emotional aspects (Conner, 2019). Behavioral engagement includes participation in academic and social activities (Archambault et al., 2019). Cognitive engagement involves self-efficacy and attentional focus (Dotterer Lowe, 2019), while emotional engagement is shaped by relationships with teachers and peers (Roorda et al., 2021). Positive teacher traits and supportive classroom environments foster greater student engagement (Rocca, 2020; Abebe et al., 2015). Smaller class sizes and engaging teaching strategies further enhance participation (MacMahon Wernsman, 2019; Prensky, 2015).

1.3. Synthesis—As seen in the light of previously conducted research, laboratory safety practices revealed that the domains, which include safety behavior, safety knowledge, safety motivation, and safety commitment, have been

seen from varying perspectives, contributing to the authenticity and richness of the data. On the other hand, based on the gathered literature, learners' engagement may be behavioral, cognitive, and emotional. The literature concurs that these engagements are triggered by the environment surrounding a learner, which includes their perspectives on laboratory safety practices.

1.4. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework of the Study—The study is anchored on the theory of planned behavior (TPB) developed by Ajzen (1991). This theory has been used to analyze various issues related to safety behavior factors. Fundamentally, the Theory of Planned Behavior was derived from the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA). Three latent constructs in TPB have clarified intention, namely behavioral attitude, subjective norm (SN), and perceived behavioral control (PBC), and possibly associated due to common external causes and correlations (Heiny et al., 2019). The TPB paradigm believes the intention to induce behavior. The study is related to the theory since laboratory practices observed in classes exemplify planned behaviors. This means that whatever is done in the class that would ensure the safety of the learners is pre-meditated to let everybody in the class observe precautionary and preventive measures that guarantee their safety. Another theory that is relevant to professional development and people's skills is emotional intelligence (EI). EI refers to the ability to recognize, understand, and regulate one's own emotions and the emotions of others (Salovey Mayer, 1990). Leaders with high levels of EI can build positive relationships, manage conflicts effectively, and create a positive school culture. Research has shown that school leaders with high EI are more effective in their roles

and positively impact teacher and student outcomes (Van Der Ploeg et al., 2018). This study is also supported by the Experiential Learning Theory by David Kolb (1984). The experiential learning theory emphasizes active learning, where students are urged to learn through experiences that can aid their ability to remember information and recall facts using this principle. Consolidating an experience is the main goal of the first two steps: concrete learning and reflective observation. The last two, active experimentation and abstract conceptualization, involve transforming an experience. Western Governors University (WGU, 2020) mentioned firsthand experiences are the finest approach to learning new things. These memories remain in your mind and aid in fact, recall and information retention. The study is anchored to theory on the basis that learners' engagement in class is a form of experiential learning. This means that the more engaged learners are in learning, the more they make learning experiential. Moreover, this study also supported the Protection Motivation Theory by Rogers (1975). It defines the factors that lead people to self-protectively when perceiving a health threat. Further, it is a frequently used framework to comprehend reactions to stimuli that alert people to a potential threat. Fear-based cues that urge people to take precautions or stop actions that could damage them or others are among these triggers (Shillair, 2020). The study is anchored on this theory in the belief that establishing safety measures and practicing them is motivated by the fact that establishing safety measures in classrooms promotes the welfare and well-being of all concerned. This is what motivates everyone to partake in observing safety practices.

The diagram above, Figure 1, is the study's conceptual framework. As seen in the diagram, the independent variable was the labo-

ratory safety practices in T.L.E. classes, with the following indicators: safety behavior, safety knowledge, safety motivation, and safety com-

Fig. 1. Conceptual Model of the Study

mitment. The dependent variable was the engagement of high school students in T.L.E. classes. Hypothesis HO1. There is no significant relationship between laboratory safety practices and the engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes. HO2. None of the indicators of laboratory safety practices significantly influences the engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes.

To better understand the terminologies used in this research, the following are given conceptual and operational definitions: Laboratory safety practices conceptually refer to the routines and other activities that are regularly observed and commonly understood by the classes

in the context of day-to-day class instruction to promote safety. Operationally, the term refers to the specific tasks, routines, and other activities that are regularly practiced and observed in T.L.E. classes to ensure nobody gets harmed, injured, or inflicted with pain as they attend to their daily instructional routines. On the other hand, the term "engagement of students" conceptually means the participation or involvement of students in all activities facilitated by teachers to acquire knowledge, skills, and values. Operationally, the term refers to the active participation of all learners in the learning opportunities facilitated by teachers in the T.L.E. classes.

2. Methodology

This chapter will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) enhanced the manuscript's quality, coherence, and precision. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—The study adopted a quantitative, descriptive, non-experimental design using the descriptive-predictive-correlational technique, which is deemed fit for determining the significant relationship between laboratory safety practices and high school students' engagement in T.L.E

classes. Quantitative research was utilized in this study to gather and utilize numerical data from a large population to determine the influence of laboratory safety practices on the engagement of learners in their T.L.E. classes. Applying this method would mean focusing on new data, collected and analyzed from a large

population in which the researcher's emotions and feelings are ignored. This subscribes to the notion of Mafuwane (2012) that quantitative research results are expected to be duplicated or repeated regardless of the process or researcher, designed to surface the relationship between variables. This research utilized a correlational technique. It was used to show the relationship (positive or negative correlation) between professional development and people's skills of school heads in cluster 4 through data analysis that would provide new insights and views about the relationship between the two variables. Correlational research was non-experimental, measuring the statistical connectedness between two uncontrollable variables.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—The respondents were the 130 junior high school students in the public secondary schools in the Division of Davao Oriental. The study's School Managers were responsible for the administration and management of their respective schools. These individuals were typically the top decision-makers in their schools. They oversee the implementation of policies, programs, and initiatives that affect the students, teachers, and staff in their schools.

2.3. *Ethical Considerations*—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. Informed Consent. The researcher obtained the consent of respondents through written informed consent. They were properly informed about the purpose of the study, and ample explanations were provided to help them better understand the reason for their participation so that they could choose whether to

participate or not. It was made clear that the respondent's involvement in the study was voluntary. If they refused to participate, they were not forced by the researcher. Besides, the researcher was cautious to ensure the respondents' psychological well-being. Written permission was secured from the respondents. The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to study the factors that hinder/promote the teacher's satisfaction with school clinic services and may contribute to the enhancement. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The study's respondents were teachers, so they are not considered vulnerable since all of them are of legal age and were not considered highly vulnerable psychologically. The researcher emphasized that the survey was set at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed. Privacy and Confidentiality. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2012, wherein the researcher assured that the data could not be traced back to the participants, who would be the real source of information to protect their identities. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the consent of the participants. Thus, to ensure that no personal data would be exposed, access was limited to the researcher alone. Risk, Benefits, and Safety - In administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation and explained thoroughly and properly the purpose and benefits of the study and the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the online survey questionnaire. Without restrictions, the respondents could ask questions related to the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not subjected to harm in any way whatsoever. Moreover, the questionnaire and interview guide used in this study did not contain any degrading or unacceptable statements offensive to the study's respondents. Likewise, this study was designed purely to collect aca-

demic information related to the study, and the participants were not asked for personal information. To minimize inconvenience, the researcher ensured the respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire online. The respondents were given the freedom not to answer questions that made them feel any psychological and emotional distress, and they would be free to withdraw as respondents to the study if they felt that they could not discuss the information that was asked of them. The researcher valued their participation and placed their welfare as the highest priority during the study. Justice. To avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents, the researcher regarded all respondents equally regardless of whether they would be respondents in the survey. The researcher was not prejudiced in choosing the respondents for the study—anybody who fits the qualifications of being permanent-regular in the purposely selected schools. During the study, the researcher made certain to respect the respondents by interrupting the routine of the respondents for as little time as possible. To compensate for the time spent during data gathering, the researcher gave tokens of appreciation to the respondents. This token was an assortment of souvenirs. The tokens were sent via courier and sealed carefully in a package. Also, each token was sanitized before being sent to your doorstep. Transparency. To provide transparency in this study, any communication about the research was done honestly and fairly. To safeguard the welfare of the participants, the researcher properly implemented the methods discussed in this study. All the necessary documents that supported the data analysis were included. Importantly, the researcher described the extent of the respondents' involvement in this study and shared how the researcher-maintained objectivity in analyzing data and presenting the study results. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that other factors, like a conflict of interest, did not influ-

ence the respondents' responses. The study's findings could be accessed by the respondent's parents and school administrators of the participating schools because the information would be made available as long as they followed proper protocol to protect the anonymity of the respondents. The researcher also acknowledged the effort of every person who contributed to the study's success; the Division of Davao City was given a furnished copy of the research results so it could be accessed by the respondents and be used for learning and further study. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment and learning materials that were ample and available during the study and completed within the time set by the researcher. The accuracy of gathering data from the respondents was ensured by encoding the respondents' ratings properly during the day when the researcher was not too tired to do them to avoid errors in encoding. Also, the analysis and results were proficient and aligned, serving as a primary basis for adequacy. Community Involvement. It was good practice to involve the community during every research phase, from planning to reporting. Hence, the researcher planned to share the findings generated with the community, and community involvement was accorded primacy in making decisions about the research agenda, appropriate methods to apply in their context, and using the results or findings. The findings of this study would then be shared with the community through gatherings, fora, and conferences.

2.4. Research Instrument—The instrument for the study was a survey questionnaire that was adapted and modified to meet the research objectives and the study population. Using a survey questionnaire is appropriate for this study because it enables the researcher to collect essential data relatively briefly. In addition, by adapting and modifying the survey questionnaire, the researcher could tailor the queries to be more pertinent and specific to the

research objectives and population under study. Experts in the field of education would validate the questionnaire that will be utilized for this study. It would then be pilot-tested to determine its validity and reliability. In this study's survey, a 5-point Likert scale was utilized. A Likert Scale is a commonly used measurement instrument in the social sciences, particularly in educational research, to assess individuals' attitudes, opinions, and perceptions regarding a particular topic. It enables respondents to articulate their level of agreement or disagreement with a statement on a scale ranging from strongly agree to disagree strongly. In this study, using a 5-point Likert Scale is appropriate because it provides a range of responses that can capture nuances in respondents' opinions or perceptions. Responses can be tabulated and statistically analyzed, making data analysis straightforward. Using a standardized scale, such as the 5-point Likert Scale, improves the reliability and validity of the collected data because it permits comparisons across studies. For the independent variable, which is the learning motivation of junior high school students toward their science classes, a modified and adapted Students' Motivation Towards Science Learning questionnaire from the study of Tuan, Chin,

and Shieh was used. The questionnaire consists of 35 items. The science learning motivation questionnaire aims to gather information about the level of motivation of junior high school students toward science subjects. The data collected from the questionnaire can help educators and the researcher identify the factors that influence student motivation and develop strategies to improve it. By understanding the factors that affect student motivation, educators can create a more engaging and effective learning environment for students. For the independent variable, value-expectancy on STEM, a modified and adapted Value-Expectancy STEM Assessment Scale questionnaire was used from the study by Abdullah and Abd Aziz (2020). The questionnaire consists of 28 items. The laboratory safety practices questionnaire aims to assess the students' safety management of laboratory practices and how these practices influence their motivation and engagement in learning and laboratory activities. Ultimately, the questionnaire aims to provide valuable insights into improving the laboratory practices of every school, primarily on the TLE subject. The Likert Scale below was used to assess the value-expectancy of junior high school students.

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	Laboratory safety practices are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Laboratory safety practices are oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Laboratory safety practices are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Laboratory safety practices are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Laboratory safety practices are never manifested.

For the dependent variable, the engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. class, a modified and adapted questionnaire was used from the study of Sumandal and Legarde (2022). The questionnaire consists of 30 items. The engagement of junior high school students in the T.L.E. class questionnaire aims to assess

the students’ multiple psychological constructs that students affect their academic performance; engagement has become one of the research factors that many educators are studying. The Likert Scale below was used to assess the value-expectancy of junior high school students.

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The engagement of Junior high school students in T.L.E. class is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Engagement of Junior high school students in T.L.E. class is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Engagement of Junior high school students in T.L.E. class is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Engagement of Junior high school students in T.L.E. class is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The engagement of Junior high school students in T.L.E. class is not manifested.

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The researcher shall facilitate the running of a survey using the reproduced validated survey instrument to gather the required data. All validated data-gathering instruments shall be submitted to the Office of the Dean of Graduate School for endorsement to the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Davao City. After the Office approves, the researcher shall seek permission from the Public Schools District Supervisor of the select junior high school in the Division of Davao Oriental to distribute the survey forms to the student respondents. During the dissemination process, the researcher shall give respondents explicit instructions on completing the survey material and explain specific points of the survey that respondents need to

clarify. After retrieving the completed survey forms, the researcher will process, organize, analyze, and interpret the data.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools were to be utilized to analyze and interpret data: Mean. This statistical tool was used to determine high school students’ safety practices and engagement levels in the T.L.E. classes. Pearson Moment Coefficient Correlation. This statistical tool would determine the significant relationship between laboratory safety practices and high school students’ engagement in the T.L.E. classes. Linear regression analysis. This was used to determine which of the domains of laboratory safety practices significantly influences high school students’ engagement in the T.L.E. classes.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the researcher’s analyses and interpretations of the data gathered. Discussions are presented categorically based on the sequence of the problem statement in the first chapter.

3.1. *Extent of Laboratory Safety Practices in terms of Safety-behavior*—Reflected in Table 1 is the Extent of Laboratory Safety Practices in terms of Safety behavior with mean and description.

Table 1. Extent of Laboratory Safety Practices in Terms of Safety Behavior

Safety Behavior	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
My T.L.E. teacher educates us on how we behave accordingly during laboratory work so we can avoid accidents.	4.04	Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher emphasizes that we need to pay attention to the details of our work to avoid hurt, injuries or the like.	4.01	Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher encourages us to show good behavior in terms of safety.	3.17	Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher demonstrates to us how to properly behave in laboratory work for our safety.	3.67	Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher gives feedback on how we behave during laboratory work in T.L.E. classes.	4.18	Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher reminds us of the different safety precautionary measures before we begin hands-on learning in T.L.E. classes.	3.97	Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher teaches us to have a positive attitude toward practicing safety during our laboratory classes in T.L.E.	3.99	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.86	Extensive

It can be seen from the table that the highest mean belongs to the statement, “My T.L.E. teacher gives feedback to how we behave during laboratory works in T.L.E. classes,” with a mean of 4.18 and a descriptive level of high. Next is the statement: My T.L.E. teacher emphasizes that we need to pay attention to the details of our work to avoid hurt, injuries, or the like, with a mean of 4.01. My T.L.E. teacher teaches us to have a positive attitude towards practicing safety during our laboratory classes in T.L.E., gaining a mean of 3.99. My T.L.E. teacher reminds us of the different safety precautionary measures before we begin hands-on learning in T.L.E. classes with the mean of 3.97. My T.L.E. teacher demonstrates how to properly behave in

laboratory work for our safety with a mean of 3.67. On the other hand, the lowest mean for the self-efficacy of junior high school students is 3.17, with a descriptive level of moderate belonging to the statement, “My T.L.E. teacher encourages us to show good behavior in terms of safety.” The research findings indicate that students exhibit high self-efficacy regarding feedback giving. This suggests that these students possess a strong determination and resilience to overcome difficulties in laboratory activities, especially when they receive feedback on their performances. However, the findings also reveal a moderate level of self-efficacy when showing good behavior. This implies room for improvement in fostering students’ motivation and enthusiasm to tackle challenging science concepts. Based on these findings, educators and curriculum developers should focus on strategies that enhance students’ engagement in laboratory safety practices. The findings from the study indicate that the highest mean score and descriptive level were observed for the statement, “When science activities are too difficult, I do not give up or settle in doing the easy parts only,” indicating that the surveyed junior high school students demonstrated a high level of determination and resilience when faced with challenging science tasks. This finding aligns with previous research that emphasizes the sig-

The statement with the highest mean of 4.16 and with a descriptive level of high belongs to, “My T.L.E. teacher teaches us how to properly handle materials and equipment as we operate them during a laboratory.” Next is the statement, “My T.L.E. teacher teaches us how to protect ourselves from the harms that our materials and equipment we use, “ gaining a mean score of 4.0; my T.L.E. teacher discusses safety measures in the laboratory with the means of 3.95, My T.L.E. teacher makes us all understand the safety measures to be observed during

nificance of self-efficacy in science learning motivation (Membiela et al., 2022). According to the literature, students with higher science self-efficacy exhibit greater confidence in their abilities and a greater willingness to successfully complete tasks (Hu et al., 2022). According to Goswami et al. (2011), safety knowledge is understanding learned hazards and safety controls through safety training. Safety knowledge and safety behavior, such as safety compliance and involvement, are related, as noted by Christian et al. (2009) and Keiser and Payne (2019). Safety raises awareness and encourages people to be more accountable and focused on their work. These findings also indicate that lecturers’ roles in safety leadership need to be clarified in light of safety concerns in university laboratories. Research shows that safety leadership can enhance safety behaviors and lower student accident and injury rates (Hill Finster, 2013; Shanmugam, 2018; Wu et al., 2008). Safety motivation and knowledge should also be investigated for a more significant effect on laboratory safety.

3.2. *Extent of Laboratory Safety Practices in terms of Safety Knowledge*—Reflected in Table is the Extent of Laboratory Safety Practices in terms of Safety knowledge with mean and description.

laboratory works in T.L.E. with the mean of 3.82, My T.L.E. teacher makes us know the advantages of practicing safety during laboratory works in T.L.E. gaining the mean of 3.60, and the statement My T.L.E. teacher teaches us what protective suits need to be worn during a laboratory class gaining the mean of 3.55, all with the descriptive equivalent of extensive meaning to say the statements on the laboratory safety practices in terms of safety knowledge is oftentimes manifested. On the contrary, the lowest statement got a mean of 3.28 and

Table 2. Extent of Laboratory Safety Practices in Terms of Safety Knowledge

Safety Knowledge	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
My T.L.E. teacher teaches us how to protect ourselves from the harm of the materials and equipment we use.	4.00	Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher makes us all understand the safety measures to be observed during laboratory work in T.L.E.	3.82	Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher teaches us how to properly handle materials and equipment as we operate them in a laboratory.	4.16	Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher discusses safety measures in the laboratory.	3.95	Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher updates us with the latest knowledge on safety practices to be observed in the laboratory classes in T.L.E.	3.28	Moderately Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher teaches us what protective suits need to be worn during a laboratory class.	3.55	Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher makes us know the advantages of practicing safety during laboratory work in T.L.E.	3.60	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.77	Extensive

with a descriptive level of moderate belongs to, “My T.L.E. teacher updates us with the latest knowledge on safety practices to be observed in the laboratory classes in T.L.E.” The research findings reveal that junior high school students demonstrate high laboratory safety practices as the teacher incorporates modeling and teaches them how to handle laboratory equipment. This suggests that students proactively engage in directed learning. The research findings indicate that the statement ” My T.L.E. teacher teaches us how to properly handle materials and equipment as we operate them during a laboratory” received the highest mean score of 4.16 and a descriptive level of high. This suggests that the surveyed students actively seek additional resources to enhance their understanding when faced with challenging science concepts. This

finding aligns with the existing literature that emphasizes the importance of active learning strategies in improving student engagement in the laboratory. In laboratory settings, educators have a significant deal of responsibility in a variety of safety measures and emergency reaction scenarios about lab safety. Teachers should ensure the security of their students, offer a wholesome workplace, and be able to assess the kinds of circumstances in which kids might meet as a consequence of their deeds. In addition, teachers should be trained within the scope of the old and new labeling systems to recognize and improve the chemicals in the laboratory. They should be able to replace old and torn labels using new pictograms. Science teachers should prepare materials (Simge Bülent, 2018). The findings highlight the significance of active

learning strategies in laboratory safety practice. The results indicate that whenever teachers are knowledgeable in the field of laboratory, they have various ways to integrate the engagement towards the students, particularly by the providing students role modeling on how to handle apparatus and equipment inside the laboratory properly and vice versa; students who actively seek relevant resources such as demonstration in order to actualize the different concepts involved in laboratory practices.

3.3. *Extent of Laboratory Safety Practices in terms of Safety Motivation*—The table reflects the Extent of Laboratory Safety Practices in terms of Safety motivation with mean and description. The statement with the highest mean of 4.63 and a very high descriptive level states, “My T.L.E. teacher reminds us of the benefits of being safe and protected during lab-

By showcasing the essentiality of safety laboratory practices and their direct impact on students’ everyday experiences, educators can foster a deeper understanding by awakening motivations. Emphasizing real-life connections and providing meaningful examples can enhance students’ motivation and engagement, ultimately encouraging them to recognize the relevance of science in their daily lives and inspiring a lifelong interest in the subject. The research findings reveal that the statement “My T.L.E. teacher reminds us of the benefits of being safe and protected during laboratory work” received the highest mean score of 4.63 and a descriptive level of very extensive. This indicates that educators must safely conduct laboratory experiments. In this regard, a desire to perform any task carefully is known as safety motivation. A person’s desire will cause them to alter their behavior. Another name for safety motivation is the psychological process that establishes safety behavior. Proximal factors, such as safety motivation, directly affect an individual’s safety

laboratory work.” On the contrary, the statement with the lowest mean, albeit interpreted as high, belongs to, “My T.L.E. teacher gives us material rewards after completing laboratory work safely.” The research findings indicate that students strongly value the affective domain in learning, as demonstrated by the highest mean of 4.63 for the statement, “My T.L.E. teacher reminds us of the benefits of being safe and protected during laboratory work.” This highlights the students’ recognition of the importance and practical application of safety inside the laboratory. On the other hand, although interpreted as high, the lowest mean for the statement, “My T.L.E. teacher gives us material rewards after completing laboratory work safely,” suggests a potential area for further exploration. Educators can focus on bridging the gap between students’ perceptions of the providing rewards.

Students’ desire to do safe laboratory experiments was theoretically described as safety motivation (Abdullah Aziz, 2020).

3.4. *Extent of Laboratory Safety Practices in terms of Safety Commitment*—Reflected in Table 6 is the Extent of Laboratory Safety Practices in terms of Safety commitment with mean and description. The statement that got the highest mean of 4.65 and with a descriptive level of 4.65 belongs to, “My T.L.E. teacher encourages us to consider safety practices in general as a way of life as well as teaches us to be responsible at all times in observing safety in the workplace” On the contrary, the statement that got the lowest mean of 4.15 albeit with a descriptive level of 4.15 belongs to, “My T.L.E. teacher makes us feel committed to practicing safety in the laboratory work.” The research findings reveal that the highest mean of 4.65 for the statement, “My T.L.E. teacher encourages us to consider safety practices in general as a way of life as well as teaches us to be responsible at all times in observing safety in the

Table 3. Extent of Laboratory Safety Practices in Terms of Safety Motivation

Safety Motivation	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
My T.L.E. teacher motivates us to pay attention and utmost care as we attend to our laboratory work.	4.11	Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher emphasizes to us that there are a number of benefits that we can enjoy for practicing safety during laboratory work.	4.33	Very Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher reminds us of the benefits of being safe and protected during laboratory work.	4.63	Very Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher encourages us to be more careful in handling materials and equipment used during laboratory work.	4.26	Very Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher makes us feel motivated to take part in practicing safety in the workplace.	4.34	Very Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher praises us or gives positive feedback after completing laboratory work where all of us are sound and safe.	3.55	Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher gives us material rewards after completing laboratory work safely.	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	4.07	Extensive

workplace” and “My T.L.E. teacher makes us realize that practicing safety during a laboratory work is a shared responsibility” suggests that students place a high value on the practical applications and real-life situations where their knowledge in laboratory safety practices can be applied.

Also, the students have accentuated that laboratory safety practices are then a shared responsibility between the teacher and the students, not only the teachers alone but also the students who are using the laboratory. On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.15 for the statement, ” My T.L.E. teacher makes us feel committed to practicing safety in the laboratory work.” indicates a slightly lower emphasis on competition with peers as a driving factor in their engagement. These findings highlight the need for educators to instill in the students to foster real-life situations as an application of safety practices. Recognizing safety does not only end on the laboratory premises; in other words, this denotes applying safety practices in a real-life scenario. Additionally, collaboration between the teacher and the students is much needed inside the laboratory. In order to proceed with a successful laboratory activity, teachers must be equipped with knowledge that can be applied to the students. On the other hand, the student must be

Table 4. Extent of Laboratory Safety Practices in Terms of Safety Commitment

Safety Commitment	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
My T.L.E. teacher encourages us to consider safety practices in general as a way of life.	4.65	Very Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher makes us feel committed to practicing safety in laboratory work.	4.15	Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher made us realize that practicing safety during laboratory work is a shared responsibility.	4.65	Very Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher makes us understand our individual contributions to the practice of safety during laboratory work.	4.39	Very Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher teaches us that it is our moral and social obligation to get involved in safety practices during laboratory work.	4.35	Very Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher encourages us to report or act immediately on incidents that threaten our safety.	4.23	Very Extensive
My T.L.E. teacher teaches us to be responsible at all times in observing safety in the workplace.	4.19	Very Extensive
Overall Mean	4.37	Very Extensive

open to the different concepts involved in laboratory safety practices. Designing learning experiences and instilling shared responsibility between teachers and students promotes curiosity, critical thinking, and a passion for laboratory activities. This finding aligns with previous literature highlighting that Townsend and Goffe (2022) emphasized that the courses to be given on laboratory safety were comprehensive. One of educators’ biggest challenges is making their students understand the importance of course content. They mention that this is necessary not only for the curriculum but also for daily life skills. Moreover, as a result, safety training is crucial for developing safety procedures and preparing students to handle situations (Lasker et al., 2019; Freitas et al., 2019). Working safely is a basic responsibility of every employee and every student. Reduce unnecessary risks, ensure that others follow regulations, and always bring

safety concerns to the attention not only on the four corners of the laboratory but also on outside laboratory premises incorporating real-life applications.

3.5. *Summary of the Extent of Laboratory Safety Practices* —Table 5 shows the extent of laboratory safety practices from the perspective of various indicators such as safety behavior, safety knowledge, safety motivation, and safety commitment. Each indicator has a calculated mean and descriptive level, which gives an idea about the students’ overall motivation towards learning. The overall mean of the laboratory safety practices is 4.35, corresponding to a Very Extensive level of motivation. This suggests that the students have a positive attitude towards learning and are motivated to engage in various laboratory activities incorporating safety practices.

Table 5. Summary of the Extent of Laboratory Safety Practices

Safety Practices	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Safety Motivation	4.33	Very Extensive
Safety Knowledge	4.39	Very Extensive
Safety Behavior	4.37	Very Extensive
Safety Commitment	4.32	Very Extensive
Overall Mean	4.35	Very Extensive

The indicator with the highest mean score is performance goal, which has a mean of $x=4.39$, indicating a very high level of motivation. This suggests that students are knowledgeable about the different laboratory practices. The second highest mean score is Safety Behavior with a mean of $x=4.37$, also indicating a very high level of safety practices. This suggests that students know how to behave inside the laboratory, instilling good behavior in knowing what to do and what not to do. The third highest mean score is Safety Motivation, with a mean of $x=4.33$, indicating a very high level of motivation. This suggests that students have a positive attitude and motivation towards safe laboratory practices. The fourth highest mean score is Safety Commitment, with a mean of $x=4.32$, also indicating a very high level of safety laboratory practices. This suggests that students are committed to a stimulating and conducive learning environment that highlights student obligations inside the laboratory. These results imply that students' attitudes regarding laboratory activities are highly protective of the lab. Teachers can improve their safety procedures by creating an engaging learning environment that promotes involvement and active engagement. They can also support the creation and application of efficient learning strategies. Additionally, encouraging students' self-efficacy views and highlighting the importance of safety measures in the classroom may be helpful since these factors can improve students' academic

performance and motivation.

3.6. *Extent of Engagement Of Junior High School Students In T.L.E. Classes In Terms of Behavioral Engagement* —Reflected in Table 6 is extent of engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes in terms of behavioral engagement with mean and description. The statements with the highest mean of 4.15 and a descriptive level of high belong to the following: "I believe all learnings I gain are helpful to me" and "I respond positively to the challenges in learning." On the contrary, the statement that got the lowest mean of 3.62, albeit with a descriptive level of high, belongs to, "I talk about T.L. E. outside of class." The research findings suggest that students highly value the importance of STEM (Science et al.) as indicated by the highest mean of 4.15 for the statements, " I believe all learnings I gain are helpful to me" and "I respond positively to the challenges in learning." This highlights a positive perception and recognition of students' significance and potential impact on their TLE Classes. However, it is worth noting that although still interpreted as high, the lowest mean of 3.62 for the statement, " I talk about T.L. E. outside of class," suggests a slightly lower level of student engagement. This finding underscores the importance of providing students with more information, exposure, and support, which leads to the understanding that engagement in TLE classes provides them with meaningful learning experiences. Moreover, it was also denoted that whenever students

encounter challenges, particularly on the subject, they instill a positive attitude in dealing with the challenges.

Table 6. Extent of Engagement of Junior High School Students in T.L.E. Classes in Terms of Behavioral Engagement

Behavioral Engagement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
I stay focused in T.L.E. class.	4.02	Extensive
I really complete my homework and answer questions on time.	3.98	Extensive
I believe all the learning I have gained has been helpful to me.	4.15	Extensive
I talk about T.L.E. outside of class.	3.62	Extensive
I keep trying even if a question that is asked is hard.	4.02	Extensive
I analyze and give my best try if the question is difficult to answer.	4.05	Extensive
I respond positively to the challenges in learning.	4.15	Extensive
I really put effort into answering questions in T.L.E. class.	4.08	Extensive
I participate in T.L.E. class by answering the teacher’s questions.	3.89	Extensive
I pay full attention to answering the posed questions.	4.05	Extensive
Overall Mean	4.01	Extensive

The research findings indicate that the statements "I believe all learnings I gain are helpful to me" and "I respond positively to the challenges in learning" received the highest mean scores of 4.15, reflecting a high level of agreement among the participants. This suggests that students recognize the importance of the TLE subject as an important and helpful factor in dealing with problems and challenges. They perceive the T.L.E. subject as important and meaningful, indicating a positive attitude and interest toward the subject. These findings align with the literature, which highlights the influential role of fundamentals of technicalities that are present in people’s daily lives as a high school

topic. Sumandal and Legarde (2022) mentioned that it is widely acknowledged that TLE is a highly skill-based subject in which teachers need to provide their students with real-world, practical, and realistic teaching-learning opportunities. Thus, students learn best in TLE class when they participate actively and get hands-on experience. Furthermore, students learn best in TLE when actively engaging in the material. Additionally, it offers educational programs that support students in gaining the values and abilities necessary to succeed in life. Added to, learners who have positive views on a concept may create an integrative motivation, which in turn may facilitate the acquisition of a deeper

understanding. It is often known that a person’s initial motivation and attitudes significantly impact their ability to acquire knowledge. People will be more successful and strongly driven to learn the TLE subject if they have a positive attitude (Syukur, 2001).

3.7. *Extent of Engagement of Junior High School Students In T.L.E. Classes In terms of Cognitive Engagement* —Reflected in Table 7 is extent of engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes in terms of cognitive engagement with mean and description. The statement that got the highest mean of 4.46 and

with a descriptive level of very high belongs to, “I think about different ways to solve a problem or answer a question.” and “I try to connect what I am learning to things I have learned before.” On the contrary, the statement that got the lowest mean, 3.75, with a descriptive level of high, belongs to, “I work for T.L.E. class to try to make sure it is right.” The research findings indicate that students have a strong knowledge of previous concepts that leads them to connect their fundamental concepts to the present: ”I try to connect what I am learning to things I have learned before.

Table 7. Extent of Engagement of Junior High School Students in T.L.E. Classes in Terms of Cognitive Engagement

Cognitive Engagement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
I think about different ways to solve a problem or answer a question.	4.46	Very Extensive
I try to connect what I am learning to things I have learned before.	4.46	Very Extensive
I analyze how a certain performance is better done before acting it out.	3.95	Extensive
I answer questions more than enough.	3.87	Extensive
I still do my best to answer when the question is hard.	3.95	Extensive
I work for the T.L.E. class to try to make sure it is right.	3.75	Extensive
I really think hard when I am asked questions in a T.L.E. class.	3.95	Extensive
I would rather answer questions than be told of the answer.	3.80	Extensive
I try to understand my mistakes when I get something wrong.	3.89	Extensive
Overall Mean	4.01	Extensive

This highlights their recognition of the potential influence and positive contributions that TLE can have in various fields, from the past to the present. “I think about different ways to solve a problem or answer a question” indi-

cates that student learning and skills have been emphasized as varied and multifaceted, which leads them to a statement. However, it is noteworthy that although still interpreted as high, the lowest mean of 3.75 for the statement, ” I

work for T.L.E. class to try to make sure it is right.," suggests a slightly lower level of confidence in their potential to achieve significant outcomes in their TLE subject. This finding underscores the importance of instilling a growth mindset and fostering a continuous learning process that learning does not end in one subject but also incorporates the concepts from the past up to the present. Educators and mentors can play a vital role in nurturing students' concepts by ensuring the intensity of the concepts that the students can instill in their long-term memories. Moreover, strategic thinking also has a huge impact on the students and how they find ways to complete tasks and solve problems. Educators must also encourage students to become multifaceted in thinking and processing learning. The research findings indicate that making sense of the present by applying historical knowledge to it is, hence, a crucial component of historical thought. Added to knowing the specific methods or techniques that students use to solve problems becomes crucial when TLE enables more flexible approaches to problem-solving. These educational systems will employ methods to identify student strategies. One

The research findings indicate that students have a solid motivation to learn TLE. High engagement in TLE classes is associated with students' academic performance. This result is consistent with a study by Delfino (2019) that found a favorable correlation between academic success and student involvement. Consequently, educators are strongly urged to identify ways to optimize student involvement, leading to significant teaching-learning opportunities for the students. Also, the student is open to a deeper understanding of the different concepts of the TLE subject. Teachers are urged to keep investigating and implementing excellent practices that maximize the educational experiences of their students. A lively and interesting learning

benefit of such self-improving systems is that they become increasingly sophisticated in analyzing student behavior and capacity to accommodate a wide range of learning modalities as their usage expands. Chadwick (2018) posits that research frameworks or specialized models can integrate cross-disciplinary knowledge as an agent of behavior change. According to Gravina et al. (2019) and Rhodes et al. (2019), knowledge, skills, and talents were the traits of behaviorally altered agents.

3.8. *Extent of Engagement of Junior High School Students in T.L.E. Classes In terms of Emotional Engagement*—Reflected in Table 8 is extent of engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes in terms of Emotional engagement with mean and description. The statement that got the highest mean of 4.65 and with a descriptive level of 4.65 belongs to, "I want to understand what we are learning in T.L.E. class" and "I often feel motivated and encouraged in a T.L.E. class" On the contrary, the statement that got the lowest mean of 4.15 albeit with a descriptive level of 4.15 belongs to, "I think that a T.L.E. class is exciting and interesting"

environment can be produced in the classroom through the dynamic interaction of differentiated instruction, active learning, technological integration, and real-world applications. Adopting a growth mentality, educators should be adaptive and flexible, always looking for new ways to motivate and empower their pupils. Furthermore, this study emphasizes how crucial it is for educators to conduct ongoing research and inquiry. Since learning is a lifelong process, it is essential to comprehend how pupils learn in order to enhance education. To create a complete picture of the complex relationship between learning styles and academic achievement, future research might examine the impact of learning styles across a variety of academic

Table 8. Extent of Engagement of Junior High School Students in T.L.E. Classes in Terms of Emotional Engagement

Emotional Engagement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
I want to understand what we are learning in T.L.E. class.	4.65	Very Extensive
I think that a T.L.E. class is exciting and interesting.	4.15	Extensive
I often feel motivated and encouraged in a T.L.E. class.	4.65	Very Extensive
I often get excited when I learn new things about T.L.E.	4.39	Very Extensive
I often feel confident when I am in a T.L.E. class.	4.35	Very Extensive
I care about learning T.L.E. lessons.	4.23	Very Extensive
I want to be in a T.L.E. class.	4.19	Very Extensive
I feel good when I am in a T.L.E. class.	4.20	Very Extensive
I enjoy learning new things in T.L.E. class.	4.22	Very Extensive
I look forward to attending my T.L.E. class.	4.25	Very Extensive
Overall Mean	4.33	Very Extensive

disciplines, grade levels, and cultural situations (Chen, 2018).

3.9. *Summary of the Engagement of Junior High School Students in T.L.E. Classes*—The overall mean for Engagement of Junior

High School Students in T.L.E. Classes of Junior High School Students is 4.00, with a high descriptive level. This indicates that the students generally have a positive attitude and high engagement toward TLE classes.

Table 9. Summary of the Engagement of Junior High School Students in T.L.E. Classes

Engagement of Junior High School Students in T.L.E. Classes	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Behavioral Engagement	3.99	Extensive
Cognitive Engagement	4.02	Extensive
Emotional Engagement	4.05	Extensive
Overall Mean	4.02	Extensive

The indicator with the highest mean is emotional engagement in TLE Classes, with a mean of 4.05 and a high descriptive level. This suggests that the students are highly engaged in TLE classes, which could lead to increased motivation and effort in dealing with different classroom activities. The second-highest indicator is cognitive engagement in TLE Classes, with

a mean of 4.02 and a high descriptive level. This indicates that the students recognize the importance and relevance of STEM fields in their lives and society, which could also contribute to their interest and motivation in pursuing STEM education and careers. According to the respondents, these findings imply that student participation in TLE classes is evident since students generally view TLE as a pleasant subject. Nonetheless, it is critical to keep offering resources and assistance to students so they can advance their knowledge and abilities in TLE programs and overcome any obstacles or difficulties they might encounter in pursuing these careers.

3.10. Significant Relationship Between Laboratory Safety Practices and Engagement of Junior High School Students in T.L.E. Classes—Table 10 presents the statistical results for the significant relationship between laboratory

safety practices and the engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes. The table provides the following information: r-value, p-value, decision on HO1 at the 0.05 level of significance, and interpretation. The statistical analysis shows a significant positive relationship between laboratory safety practices and the engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes in the Davao Oriental division. The r value of .708 indicates a strong positive correlation between the two variables. The p-value of 0.000 suggests that the relationship between the variables is significant, with a 0.05 significance level. The rejection of the null hypothesis (HO1) at a 0.05 level of significance means that the relationship between laboratory safety practices and engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes is never by accident. Instead, it is probable that a true correlation exists between these variables.

Table 10. Significant Relationship Between Laboratory Safety Practices and Engagement of Junior High School Students in T.L.E. Classes

Laboratory Safety Practices	r	p-value	Decision on HO1 at 0.05 level of significance	Interpretation
Engagement of Junior High School Students in T.L.E. Classes	0.708	0.000	Reject HO1	There is a significant relationship.

3.11. Domain of Laboratory Safety Practices and Engagement of Junior High School Students in T.L.E. Classes—Table 11 presents the results of a linear regression analysis that examines the relationship between laboratory safety practices and the engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes in the Davao Oriental division. The table features two domains of laboratory safety practices that sig-

nificantly influence the engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes. The table presents unstandardized coefficients (B), standard errors, standardized coefficients (Beta), T-values, and significance levels for each indicator. Additionally, the table highlights the decision on HO2 and its interpretation. Finally, the table includes key statistics such as the R-value, R², F-value, and P-value.

The overall model shows a strong positive relationship between laboratory safety practices and the engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes in the Davao Oriental division. The R-value of .859 indicates a strong correlation between the two variables. This implies that as laboratory safety practices increase,

engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes also increases. The R-squared value of .730 shows that the model explains 73 percent of the variance in engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes, indicating a good fit for the data.

Table 11. Domain of Laboratory Safety Practices and Engagement of Junior High School Students in T.L.E. Classes

Laboratory Safety Practices	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.	Decision	Interpretation
Constant	-0.002	0.399		-0.004	0.996		
Behavioral Engagement	0.418	0.112	0.285	3.721	0.000	Reject HO2	Significant
Cognitive Engagement	-2.507	0.795	-1.604	-3.152	0.002	Reject HO2	Significant
Emotional Engagement	1.482	0.366	0.913	4.050	0.000	Reject HO2	Significant

R = .859; R² = .737, F-value = 66.902; p-value = 0.000

The F-value of .737 with a p-value of 66.902 indicates that the overall model is statistically significant, and the null hypothesis can be rejected, suggesting that there is a relationship between laboratory safety practices and engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes in the Davao Oriental division. The comprehensive findings from the regression analysis

reveal significant implications between laboratory safety practices and the engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes in the Davao Oriental division. The findings demonstrate the significance of several important motivational variables, including self-efficacy, performance goals, accomplishment goals, and learning environment stimulation.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the summary of the findings, the conclusions based on the findings, and the recommendations generated from the findings and conclusions. The study was conducted to determine whether there is a significant relationship between laboratory safety practices and the engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes in the Davao Oriental division. He studies also analyzed the extent of laboratory safety practices in terms of safety behavior, safety knowledge, safety motivation, and safety commitment. Moreover, the extent of junior high school students' value-expectancy on science, technology, engineering, and mathematics, when analyzed in terms of perceived value of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics fields and expectations for success in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics careers, was also identified. This study sought to find the relationship between learning motivation and value-expectancy in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics in addition to its primary objective of finding this relationship. To find the answers, the researcher surveyed junior high school students in selected schools in the Division of Davao Oriental. The researcher employed a descriptive-correlation method of research, using an adapted questionnaire as the research instrument. The statistical tools used in interpreting and analyzing the data were Mean, Pearson

Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson r , and linear regression. The findings of the study were as follows. Summary of the Extent of Laboratory Safety Practices Laboratory activities in terms of incorporates safety practices in terms of Safety Motivation (4.33), safety knowledge (4.39), and Safety Behavior (4.32). The overall mean is 4.35, with a descriptive rating of very extensive. Similarly, The Summary of the Engagement of Junior High School Students in T.L.E. Classes in terms of Behavioral engagement (3.99), cognitive engagement (4.02), and emotional engagement (4.02) has an overall mean of 4.02, with a descriptive rating of extensive. The r value of .708 indicates a strong positive correlation between the two variables. The p -value of 0.000 suggests that the relationship between the variables is significant, with a 0.05 significance level. The rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0) at a 0.05 level of significance means that the relationship between laboratory safety practices and engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes is never by accident. Instead, a true correlation probably exists between these variables. The F -value of .737 with a p -value of 66.902 indicates that the overall model is statistically significant, and the null hypothesis can be rejected. This suggests that there is a relationship between laboratory safety practices and the engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes in the Davao Oriental division.

4.1. Conclusions—Based on the study's findings, the following conclusions were presented: The Extent of Laboratory Safety Practices Laboratory activities incorporating safety practices regarding safety motivation, knowledge, and behavior were extensive. The Engagement of Junior High School Students in T.L.E. Classes in terms of Behavioral, cognitive, and emotional engagement has an overall descriptive rating of extensive. There was a significant relationship between laboratory safety practices and the engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes. All the laboratory safety practices significantly influence the engagement of junior high school students in T.L.E. classes. The discovery of a strong correlation between junior high school students' participation in T.L.E. programs and laboratory safety procedures has substantial ramifications for educators, legislators, and parents/guardians. This suggests that junior high school students' positive expectations and participation in T.L.E. classes are more likely to come from students who demonstrate higher levels of laboratory practice. It implies that encouraging and improving safety laboratory procedures might favor students' perceptions of the worth and significance of T.L.E. classes, raising participation and engagement and boosting academic achievement in these subjects.

4.2. Recommendations—Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are put forward to those concerned: For educators and legislators, the conclusion that laboratory safety procedures are widespread has significant ramifications. Students with a high level of learning motivation are driven to participate in various academic activities and have a good attitude toward learning. This suggests that they may be more likely to finish their tasks, actively engage in class discussions, and look for chances to learn more. Teachers may, therefore, take advantage of this high motivation by creating dynamic and exciting learning opportunities that match the interests and objectives of their pupils. Educators may maintain and augment students' enthusiasm for education by integrating experiential learning, real-world applications, and student-centered methodologies. School Administrators. One of their accountabilities drives them to pursue the school's safe and protective spaces. The more they may gain perspectives, especially derived from this research study, the more they

understand what needs to be prioritized in promoting the overall safety and protection of all academic community members. Teachers may create lesson plans highlighting the practical applications of TLE principles, fostering intrinsic motivation, and offering meaningful and pertinent learning experiences. Legislators can fund extracurricular TLE activities that pique students' interests and stimulate their curiosity, support efforts that foster a healthy TLE learning environment, and offer resources for teacher professional development in motivation-enhancing techniques. Parents and guardians may support their children by encouraging their intrinsic motivation, giving them opportunities for practical TLE experiences, and cultivating a good attitude toward TLE learning. The study was beneficial to teachers in that understanding the dynamics of safety practices in laboratories makes them aware, ready, and responsive to any event that threatens the safety of their classes. Data from this research study allows them to gain perspectives on safety practices and learners' engagement in the learning process. Students. All efforts collectively exerted by the academic community, particularly on matters pertaining to their safety and learning engagement, benefit learners. This means that when school authorities and teachers work hand in hand to promote safety and guarantee learning engagement, students are deemed beneficiaries of all these undertakings of a school. Parents. Parents were one beneficiary of this study since the practice of safety and the engagement of learners would make them feel at ease and secure as they entrust their children to the care and custody of teachers and school authorities.

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